

Potential of Sustainable Seri-bioeconomy

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Sericulture, the ancient practice of silk production and beautiful fabrics, blends tradition with modern society, contributing to a sustainable circular economy. By efficiently utilizing resources and repurposing silk industry wastes like spent cocoon and silkworm pupal waste into an array of diverse valuable products, sericulture has the untapped potential towards the creation of a closed-loop system.

As a bioeconomy enterprise, sericulture promotes economic growth and development in the rural areas. Here we will discuss the contribution of sericulture, emphasizing its role in utilizing biomass resources for silk production and minimizing waste. Aligning the trajectory of seri-bioeconomy with the principles of circular economy and sustainable development goals (SDGs) by converting waste into value-added products, such as organic fertilizers and food items would boost resource efficiency and rural economic development.

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